

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

NEW TECHNOLOGY OF HEAT-INSULATING PERLITE CONCRETE PRODUCTS

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Abstract

The article presents the results of research on the development of compositions and technology of heat-insulating perlite concrete. When using expanded perlite obtained from imported raw materials (Armenia), samples were obtained with a density of 200-350 kg/m³, compressive strength of 0.15-0.75 MPa, thermal conductivity in a dry state of 0.054-0.077 W/(m°C). Samples of perlite concrete based on expanded perlite from a Kazakhstani deposit were characterized by the following indicators: density - 300-350 kg/m³, compressive strength 0.51-0.78 MPa, thermal conductivity coefficient in a dry state 0.075-0.078 W/(m°C)

Keywords: Perlite, perlite concrete, thermal insulation, density, strength, thermal conductivity.

The problem of heat saving in recent years has become one of the priority areas in the world, and, accordingly, also in the Republic of Kazakhstan. This is due to the high fuel consumption for heating and maintaining a comfortable thermal regime in residential buildings and, accordingly, the need to save fuel and energy resources. Thus, according to foreign specialists from the "Isover" company, the largest share of produced oil (40%) is used for heating buildings, 32% for obtaining fuel for cars, and only 28% for industrial needs. With such a scenario of fuel consumption, the need for the use of highly efficient heat-insulating materials for insulating the external structures of buildings and structures becomes obvious.

Thus, the calculations carried out according to the normative indicators of thermal protection of enclosing structures show that in the case of mounting a wall made of ordinary solid ceramic bricks, the thickness of the outer structure for the conditions of Almaty should

be about 1.4 m, and for the conditions of Astana - more than 2 m. Therefore, the most widespread is the construction of frame houses in which the supporting elements are structures made of monolithic reinforced concrete or metal, and the walls are a self-supporting system with effective heat-insulating materials.

Figure 1 presents comparative data showing the relationship between the amount of heat passing through a material and its thickness. From the presented data, it can be seen that only two types of products can be successfully used as insulators: these are foam plastics and mineral wool products.

With a high thermal insulation capacity, mineral wool boards and foam plastics still have two unfavorable aspects: the first is a hidden danger that can manifest itself during the operation of residential buildings, and specifically, environmental insecurity for apartment residents, and the second is fragility, insufficient resistance to fires [1 -2].

Figure 1 - Thicknesses of various materials providing equal thermal characteristics

Danger to humans are toxic substances emitted from polymers of mineral wool (basalt) plates (phenol, formaldehyde) or from polystyrene foam plates (styrene). According to studies [2], the sanitary and epidemiological station needs to revise the procedure for issuing certificates for the admission of materials for housing construction. Of particular danger is styrene (the monomer from which polystyrene is obtained, and then expanded polystyrene), in which the value of the maximum permissible concentration (MPC) is 1500 times less than, for example, that of carbon monoxide. Styrene is a condensed aromatic compound that has one or more benzene nuclei in its molecule, and, like similar substances (benzene, benzpyrene, benzanthracene), it has increased cumulative properties: it accumulates in the liver and is not excreted. Substances of this group are particularly dangerous. For example, benzpyrene is an active carcinogen with MPC equal to 0.000001 mg/m^3 .

It is believed that in the process of polymerization (obtaining polystyrene), toxicity is theoretically eliminated. But it must be borne in mind that, firstly, the polymerization process does not go to the end, by 97-98%, and before using polystyrene, it is necessary to subject it to “degassing”; secondly, the polymerization process is reversible, therefore, polymers are constantly decomposed (destruction process) under the influence of light, oxygen, ozone, water, mechanical and ionizing influences, and especially under the influence of heat [3]

Regarding the durability of the plaster layer applied to mineral wool or polystyrene foam boards, the following data are available. Officially, by eight European countries, the service life of facade systems of bonded thermal insulation is taken to be at least 25 years [4] under the conditions that:

- the system was certified by an independent body after the work was completed;
- there are confirmations of delivery of materials by one supplier;

- the work was carried out strictly in accordance with the current technological regulations;

- the system is properly operated, that is, every 6-7 years, the cracks that have appeared are grouted and puttied, the entire facade is repainted.

Kazakhstan has a sharp continental climate, in which during the day the temperature can change from positive to negative. In such conditions, the European standards adopted for the durability of thermal insulation facade systems require changes and revisions taking into account experimental, as well as field studies. Unfortunately, such studies are not carried out in Kazakhstan, and from the experience of Russia it is known that in Samara the facade layer in houses is destroyed after 3-4 years of operation and this leads to huge unplanned costs for repairing the outer heat-insulating layer [5]. In the article by O.A. Lobov and A.I. Ananiev [6] states the emergency state of facade systems with a lined plaster layer applied to soft insulation over a fiberglass mesh in the 5-7th year of operation of houses.

Expanded perlite-based materials can be classified as effective heat-insulating products, due to the low thermal conductivity and density of this material. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the “Union-Perlit” company organized the production of expanded perlite based on imported raw materials, in particular, imported from Armenia and Georgia. The light, highly porous aggregate obtained at the enterprise is mainly sold in the construction industry as one of the components of dry plaster mixture and in agriculture for soil application as a water-retaining component. At the same time, it seems very promising to obtain heat-insulating products on its basis, which is constrained by the lack of developments in this area and the corresponding equipment. The reason for this situation lies in the difficulty of obtaining a homogeneous mixture by mixing a small volume of cement paste with grains of expanded perlite. For example, to obtain a material with a density of 300 kg/m^3 based on expanded perlite with a bulk density of 75 kg/m^3 , approximately 1.4 m^3 of aggregate is required to

be mixed with a cement paste with a volume of only 0.21 m³. And this is with a water-cement ratio (W/C) equal to 1. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the high water demand, as well as the fragility and low strength of expanded perlite grains, which can be largely crushed during mixing. Therefore, factories that previously produced heat-insulating perlite concretes using fuel-energy-intensive technology could not compete with other materials and were forced to close.

In particular, the casting technology for obtaining heat-insulating plates from expanded perlite is carried out in the following way [7]. For 1 m³ of expanded perlite, 125-135 kg of cement and about 35 kg of asbestos are consumed. The raw mixture is prepared in the following sequence: first, water is poured into the mortar mixer (about 850 liters of water per 1 m³ of expanded perlite), then asbestos is loaded, cement and expanded perlite are poured. After the introduction of expanded perlite, the mass is stirred for 1.5 minutes and poured into molds. Products molded at a specific pressure of 0.05 MPa are pushed out of the press mold onto a perforated pallet. Hardening takes place in special chambers, where steaming and drying are combined. First, the products are kept at a temperature of 150 °C for 4 hours, then at a temperature of 80 °C for 6-8 hours, after which the temperature rises sharply to 150 °C and the products are dried to a residual moisture content of 15-20%.

The perlite-cement products obtained in this way were intended for thermal insulation of industrial equipment and pipelines at temperatures of insulated surfaces up to 600 °C.

As can be seen from the above data, in addition to the complexity and energy intensity of the technology, the raw mix contains a significant amount of asbestos, which is generally prohibited for use in European countries.

Interest in the revival of heat-insulating perlite concrete slabs is caused not only by the need to expand the range of products, but also by a sharp increase in the cost of basalt slabs, which are used on a massive scale in housing construction. So, for example, the cost of 1 m³ of P100 basalt slabs, that is, with a density of 100 kg/m³, exceeds 45,000 tenge (more than 90 euros). In addition, the binders used in the technology of basalt products are imported material, which predetermines Kazakhstan's import dependence on foreign countries.

When conducting research on the development of technology, expanded perlite sand grade P75 of the Union-Perlit company based on the Aragatsky deposit (Armenia), as well as sand grade P180 from an experimental batch obtained by expanding raw materials from the Aigul deposit (Kazakhstan) were used. The results of X-ray diffraction analysis of the samples are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of expanded perlite sand of the Aigul (a) and Aragats (b) deposits.

As expected, both samples consist of an amorphous phase, and the perlite of the Aragats deposit is 100%, and the presence of an insignificant amount of quartz is found in the perlite of the Aigul deposit. As binders, cements of domestic factories were used, the physical and mechanical characteristics of which are presented in Table. 1-3.

Table 1

Physical and mechanical properties of Portland cements

Indicators	Bukhtarma plant	Shymkent plant	Semipalatinsk plant
Specific surface, cm ² /g	4 100	2 800	3 300
Normal density, %	25	24	27
Setting time, h-min:			
Start	1-15	1-30	1-45
Finish	2-30	4-25	2-50
Compressive strength after 28 days, MPa	49,5	34,3	42,7

Table 2

Chemical composition of clinkers from Bukhtarma, Shymkent and Semipalatinsk plants

Plant	Content of oxides, %						Loss on ignition, %
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	
Bukhtarma	21,48	6,03	4,22	65,29	0,68	0,39	0,32
Shymkent	20,36	7,12	3,18	66,41	0,71	0,42	0,45
Semipalatinsk	21,83	4,59	3,92	66,12	1,19	0,38	0,12

Table 3

Mineralogical composition of Portland cements

Manufacturer	The content of the main minerals			
	C ₃ S	C ₂ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF
Bukhtarma	65,97	12,74	7,81	10,83
Shymkent	63,19	10,72	13,46	9,67
Semipalatinsk	66,79	12,21	5,50	11,92

In addition to the main raw materials, various additives were used in the work, in particular, microfibrers, inorganic salts, surface-active substances (surfactants), hyperplasticizers, the characteristics of which corresponded to the passport data for these materials.

The second stage of the work involved determining the method of mixing and molding perlite concrete, since the low strength and, accordingly, the high fragility of perlite grains do not allow preparing the molding sand as, for example, in the production of expanded clay concrete. In this case, it is also necessary to take into account the low consumption of Portland cement per unit volume of the mixture compared to the volume of expanded perlite, which differ by one order of magnitude.

Various sequences of introducing raw materials into the mixer were tested, including water and additives. As a result of numerous experiments, the most optimal variant of the method of mixing the mixture is the variant in which a porous cement paste is first prepared with an excess amount of water. Then, with the mixer running, perlite and microfiber are introduced, and the mixture is additionally mixed for 1-2 minutes.

Water-soluble additives, including calcium chloride, liquid glass and surfactants, are introduced together with mixing water, microfiber - together with perlite.

The selection of the composition of perlite concrete was carried out separately on expanded perlite from imported raw materials and separately from local raw materials from the Aigul deposit, as well as from their mixture. This is due to a significant difference between these highly porous aggregates in bulk density

(the main characteristic of such materials) and, accordingly, in density in a piece of grain.

An analysis of the fractional compositions of expanded perlite sands obtained from domestic and imported raw materials shows the following (Table 4). In accordance with the classification according to GOST 10832-2009 (Expanded perlite sand and crushed stone), expanded perlite sand with a grain size of 0.16 to 1.25 mm, obtained by roasting the perlite rock of the Armenian deposit, corresponds to the FES grade (fine expanded sand). But at the same time, the volume of the dusty part of the sand, that is, grains smaller than 0.16 mm, is 24.5%, while in the specified standard their content should not exceed 10%. Therefore, during the experiments, the excess volume of the dusty fraction of sand grains was removed. It should be noted that expanded perlite from imported raw materials is characterized by a rather low average density (55-85 kg/m³), but at the same time increased brittleness and brittleness of the grains. All these factors were taken into account when conducting research on the optimization of the compositions and technology of heat-insulating perlite concrete.

The expanded perlite sand of the Aigul deposit corresponds to the MES grade (medium expanded sand). The dusty volume of grains only slightly exceeds their content allowed by GOST 10832-2009. The positive qualities of perlite grains from local raw materials include their higher strength. At the same time, their increased density (180 kg/m³) does not make it possible to obtain material with a density of 200-250 kg/m³, which are more efficient in terms of heat engineering.

Table 4

Granulometric composition of expanded perlite sand from "Union-Perlit"

Name	Residues on sieves, %						
	5	2,5	1,25	0,63	0,315	0,16	0,16<
Expanded perlite on imported raw materials	-	-	3,3	6,82	33,0	32,4	24,5
The same, in the domestic	-	0,35	3,65	11,5	40,2	31,2	12,1

The influence of the consumption of perlite, cement of various plants, the concentration and consumption of additives, as well as technological factors was investigated. Samples of various sizes were molded: plates 400x220x50; blocks 222x70.7x70.7; cubes 70.7x70.7x70.7 mm (Fig. 2).

Figure 3. Perlite concrete samples

As a result of experimental work, the optimal compositions of perlite-concrete materials of medium density were determined, according to the classification of heat-insulating materials (Tables 5-9).

Table 5

Compositions of perlite concrete from expanded perlite sand grade P75, obtained by expanding imported raw materials

Components	Consumption of raw materials per 1 m ³ of perlite concrete, at density, kg/m ³			
	200	250	300	350
Perlite, m ³	1,4	1,4	1,4	1,4
Cement, kg	110	160	205	250
Liquid glass, kg	0,6	0,8	1,1	1,3
Calcium chloride, kg	1,2	1,4	1,6	1,8
Surfactant, l	0,6	0,5	0,4	0,4
Polypropylene fiber, kg	0,36	0,38	0,40	0,42

Table 6

Physical and mechanical properties of perlite concrete on expanded perlite sand from imported raw materials and cement grade M400 D20

Grade by density	Average density, kg/m ³	Compressive strength after 28 days of hardening*, MPa	Thermal conductivity coefficient, W/(m·°C)
D200	220	0,11	0,056
D250	265	0,22	0,065
D300	320	0,38	0,072
D350	360	0,55	0,078

* According to GOST 25820-2014, lightweight concrete grades D200 and D250 in terms of strength are not standardized.

Table 7

Physical and mechanical properties of perlite concrete on expanded perlite from imported raw materials and cement grade M500 D0

Grade by density	Average density, kg/m ³	Compressive strength after 28 days of hardening*, MPa	Thermal conductivity coefficient, W/(m·°C)
D200	220	0,15	0,054
D250	265	0,28	0,064
D300	320	0,45	0,072
D350	360	0,75	0,077

Perlite-concrete materials of grade D300 and D350 were obtained on expanded perlite from the raw materials of the Aigul deposit (Tables 8-9).

Table 8

Indicators of perlite concrete based on raw materials from the Aigul deposit and cement grade M400 D20

Consumption of the main raw material				Indicators			
with grade by density							
D300		D350		D300		D350	
Perlite, m ³	Cement, kg	Perlite, m ³	Cement, kg	R _{sz} , MPa	λ, W/(m·°C)	R _{sz} , MPa	λ, W/(m·°C)
1,1	102	1,1	140	0,38	0,076	0,65	0,079

Table 9

Indicators of perlite concrete based on raw materials from the Aigul deposit and cement grade M500 D0

Consumption of the main raw material				Indicators			
with grade by density							
D300		D350		D300		D350	
Perlite, m ³	Cement, kg	Perlite, m ³	Cement, kg	R _{sz} , MPa	λ, W/(m·°C)	R _{sz} , MPa	λ, W/(m·°C)
1,1	102	1,1	140	0,51	0,075	0,78	0,078

The study of the microstructure of the samples (Fig. 4) shows the high porosity of the expanded perlite sand grains. Moreover, the sand on the basis of the Aragats deposit is a hollow hemisphere of various shapes (Fig. 3, top row), which provides, on the one hand, a low density, on the other hand, an adequately low strength. The higher density and, accordingly, the

strength of the grains of expanded perlite sand of the Aigul deposit (Fig. 3, bottom row) is explained by the fact that the grains are solid granules. In this case, the granules are not hollow, but represent a porous frame. Due to the low consumption of cement, the layers of hardened cement paste are practically not visible in the samples.

Figure 4. Macrostructure of perlite-concrete samples made on the basis of the Aragats (a) and Aigul (c) deposits

Thus, the research results showed the fundamental possibility of obtaining heat-insulating perlite concretes with an average density of 200-250 kg/m³ and satisfactory strength characteristics with high heat-shielding properties of the material. In the future, it is planned to conduct research to improve the strength characteristics of perlite-concrete materials while maintaining a particularly low density.

References

1. Kalgin A.A. Some aspects of environmental safety in the production and use of building materials. *Stroitel'nye materialy*. - 2003. No. 2. - S. 44-45.
2. Gusev B.V., Dementiev V.M., Mirotvortsev I.I. Norms of maximum permissible concentrations for building materials of housing construction // *Construction materials, equipment, technologies of the XXI century*. - 1999. No. 5. - S. 20-21.
3. Grassi N. Chemistry of polymer degradation processes. - M., 1959.
4. Catalog of external thermal insulation systems "Baucolor". - M., 1997.
5. Zhukov V.I., Evseev L.D. Typical disadvantages of external insulation of buildings with expanded polystyrene // *Stroitel'nye materialy*. - 2007. No. 6. - S. 27-31.
6. Lobov O.I., Ananiev A.I. Durability of the facing layers of the outer walls of multi-storey buildings with an increased level of thermal insulation // *Stroitel'nye materialy*. - 2008. No. 4. - S. 56-59.
7. Gorlov Yu.P., Merkin A.P., Ustenko A.A. Technology of thermal insulation materials. - M.: Stroyizdat, 1980. - 399 p.